

Contribution to the inventory of Bryophytes of the Mamora's forest (Atlantic Morocco)

Khadija AHAYOUN¹, Mohamed CHLIYEH², Amina OUZZANI TOUHAMI³, Rachid BENKIRANE⁴ and Allal DOUIRA⁵

¹⁻⁵ *Laboratoire de Botanique, Biotechnologie et Protection des Plantes (LBBPT), Département de Biologie, Faculté des Sciences Université Ibn Tofail, B.P. 133, Kénitra, Morocco*

E-mail: douiraallal@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

Forty four bryophyte species (44) (16 mosses; 5 hepatics and 3 anthocerotales) were identified in the forest of Mamora (Atlantic Morocco). Among these species eighteen (18) taxa are new to the bryological flora of Mamora, five (5) are rare taxa.

Keywords: Inventory, Bryophytes, Mamora forest, Morocco.

INTRODUCTION

The bryological flora of Morocco is poorly studied. There is no recent flora to this diverse group, but we dispose a catalog of the Morocco's bryophytes, which sets out on a synthesis bryological diversity of Morocco and contains valuable information on local distribution of species (Ahayoun *et al.*, 2013).

620 species have been identified in different regions of Morocco (Ahayoun *et al.*, 2013), including thirty two (32) were reported in the forest of Mamora (Corbière, 1913a, 1913b; Amann, 1924; Braun-Blanquet *et al.*, 1924; Gattefossé *et al.*, 1932 ; Gattefossé, 1932; Maire

and Werner , 1934; Jelenc, 1955a, 1966, 1967; Jovet-Ast, 1955c,1955d, 1956c; Ahayoun *et al.*, 2007, 2008, 2009).

Following the example of these previous crossing harvests conducted by botanists, the forest of Mamora had never been the subject since the richness review and the bryophytes biodiversity. This is in order to fill certain gaps that we have undertaken the inventory of the bryological flora of this area. This gave us new for the region of Mamora.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study zone:

Morocco: Mamora Forest Canton A Group IV (GIV), Taicha site

This study concerns an area of the Mamora forest, which is naturally divided into five (5) cantons restricted by the valleys of the wadis as Fouarat, Smento, Tiflet and Tourizet appointed respectively from the west to the east: Canton A, B, C, D and E. The cantons are themselves

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divided into smaller units called groups (G), which are in number of 33. (Cf. Fig. 1).

The site of Taicha, Group IV (GIV) of the Canton A, subject of our study, is located absolutely in the west of the Mamora forest, positioned between the city of Kenitra to the north, the city of Salé in the southwest and the Oued Fouarat in the East. Ecologically, the site Taicha canton A (GIV) is under sub-humid bioclimatic atmospheres, soils are sands of varying depth on clay; they rely on a marl substrate of Miocene or Pliocene sandstone (Fraval *et al.*, 1997).

The average annual precipitation is 600 mm, with a large inter-annual variability. The mean temperature of the warmest month (August) is 27.5 ° C and the average of the coldest month (January) is 6.9 ° C.

The maximum monthly relative humidity is between 90 and 94% with minimum in the summer and maximum in the winter.

METHODOLOGY

Because of the Mediterranean climate of Morocco, bryophytes begin to appear after the autumn and winter rains, but the fruiting bodies are observed only during the spring. Excursions carried out regularly in different parts of the Mamora forest allowed the collection a number of specimens. The samples are photographed before and after harvested and brought to the laboratory for microscopic and macroscopic studies.

Species determination was performed using specialized works and keys of determination (Boulay, 1904; Lacouture, 1905; Trabut, 1941; Augier, 1966; Pierrot, 1982; Douin, 1986; Jovet-Ast, 1961, 1966, 1986; Jahns, 1989; Smith, 1990; Watson, 1981; Bailly *et al.*, 2004; Boudier *et al.*, 2006; Faubert, 2007; Casas, 2009).

Species preceded by an asterisk (*) for the new Mamora; (**) Represent Moroccan rare species.

Table 1: List of bryophytes growing in the Mamora forest.

Species	Families
Mosses	
* <i>Brachythecium rutabulum</i> (Hedw.) Schimp	<i>Brachytheciaceae</i> Schimp.
<i>Brachythecium velutinum</i> (Hedw.) Schimp.	
* <i>Bryum argenteum</i> Hedw.	<i>Bryaceae</i> Schwägr.
* <i>Bryum caespiticium</i> Hedw.	
<i>Bryum capillare</i> Hedw.	
<i>Bryum dichotomum</i> Hedw.	
* <i>Pleuridium acuminatum</i> Lindb.	<i>Ditrichaceae</i> Limpr.
<i>Fissidens bryoides</i> Hedw.	<i>Fissidentaceae</i> Schimp.
* <i>Entosthodon fascicularis</i>	<i>Funariaceae</i> Schwägr.
<i>Funaria hygrometrica</i> Hedw.	
* <i>Physcomitrium pyriforme</i> Brid.	
<i>Orthorichum diaphanum</i> Schrad. ex Brid	<i>Orthotrichaceae</i> Arn.
<i>Syntrichia laevipila</i> Brid	<i>Pottiaceae</i> Schimp.
<i>Timmiella barbuloidea</i> (Brid.) Mönk	
<i>Tortula muralis</i> Hedw.	
* <i>Trichostomum crispulum</i> Bruch.	
Hepatics	
<i>Corsinia coriandrina</i> (Spreng.) Lindb.	<i>Corsiniaceae</i> Engl.
<i>Fossombronia caespitifformis</i> De Not. ex Rabenh.	<i>Fossombroniaceae</i> Hazsl.
* <i>Frullania dilatata</i> (L.) Dum.	<i>Jubulaceae</i> H. Klinggr.
* <i>Lunularia cruciata</i> (Linnaeus) Dum.,	<i>Lunulariaceae</i> H. Klinggr.
<i>Oxymitra incrassata</i> (Brotero) Sergio & Sim-Sim	<i>Oxymitraceae</i> Müll. Frib. ex Grolle
<i>Riccia atomarginata</i> Levier	<i>Ricciaceae</i> Rchb.
<i>Riccia bicarinata</i> Lindb.	
(**)* <i>Riccia canaliculata</i> Hoffm.	
(**)* <i>Riccia cavernosa</i> Hoffm.	
<i>Riccia ciliifera</i> Link	
<i>Riccia ciliifera</i> fo. <i>pedemontana</i> (Steph.) Mull.	
(**)* <i>Riccia crozalsii</i> Lev.	
<i>Riccia crystallina</i>	
* <i>Riccia fluitans</i> L.	
* <i>Riccia glauca</i> L.	
<i>Riccia gougetiana</i>	
* <i>Riccia huebeneriana</i> var. <i>cavernosa</i> (Hoffm.) Ast	
* <i>Riccia lamellosa</i> Raddi	
<i>Riccia macrocarpa</i> Lev.	
<i>Riccia sorocarpa</i> Bisch	
(**)* <i>Riccia sorocarpa</i> var. <i>heegii</i> Schiffn.	
* <i>Riccia warnstorffii</i> Limpr. Ex Warnst.	
<i>Sphaerocarpos michelii</i> Bell.	<i>Sphaérocarpaceae</i> Heeg.
* <i>Targionia hypophylla</i> L.	<i>Targioniaceae</i> Dumort.
* <i>Targionia lorbeeriana</i> Müll.Frib.	
Anthocerot	
(**)* <i>Anthoceros agrestis</i> Paton	<i>Anthocerotaceae</i> Dumort.
<i>Phaeoceros laevis</i> (L.) Prosk.	
<i>Phymatoceros bulbiculosus</i> (Brot.) Stotler, W. T. Doyle & Crand. Stotl	

Figure-2. Plants *in situ* and structures of Morocco rare taxa — a: *Riccia cavernosa* Hoffm.— plants *in situ*; b, c: spores of *Riccia canalicata* Hoffm. , b: distal side, c: proximal side, d: spore, distal side (DS) Tubercled of *Anthoceros agrestis* Paton; e: cross section of a lobe of *Riccia crozalsii* Lev.; f-g: *Riccia sorocarpa* var. *heegii* Schiffn. : f: proximal face spore; g: cross section of a lobe showing on the dorsal surface of the papilla thallus X400.

In the list of inventoried taxa are presented successively mosses, hepatics and anthocerotes. The nomenclature of this contribution is based on that of Hill *et al.* (2006) for the Mosses and that of Ros *et al.* (2007) for hepatics and anthocerotes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The final list contains 44 species of bryophytes in 15 families. They grow on the sandy soil; rocks; cork of *Quercus suber* and beside dayas, on dry wadis funds (Table 1 and Figure 2).

A list of 44 taxa of bryophytes was observed in the study site (Mamora forest: Atlantic Morocco), including 16 taxa are mosses, 25 hepatics and 3 anthocerotes.

Among the 16 taxa of mosses reported in our study:

Seven (7) species are new to Mamora (*Brachythecium rutabulum* (Hedw.) Schimp.;

Bryum argenteum Hedw.; *Bryum caespiticium* Hedw.; *Entosthodon fascicularis* (Hedw.) Müll. Hal., *Physcomitrium pyriforme* Brid.; *Trichostomum crispulum* Bruch and *Pleuridium acuminatum* Lindb);

The hepatic class is represented by 25 species, divided into eight (08) families, among these species:

Ten (10) taxa are new to the Mamora forest: *Riccia crystallina* L. Emend. Raddi; *Riccia fluitans* L.; *Riccia glauca* L.; *Frullania dilatata* (L.) Dum.; *Riccia lamellosa* Raddi., *Riccia warnstorffii* Limpr. Ex Warnst, *Targionia lorbeeriana* Müller Frib.; *Targionia hypophylla* L.; *Riccia canaliculata* Hoffm; *Riccia sorocarpa* var. *heegii* Schiffn.

Five (05) taxa are rare under previous authors (Jovet-Ast, 1956; Jovet-Ast & Bischler, 1966; Smith, 1990 and B.L Chowdharyl, 2014) (*Riccia canaliculata*; *Riccia crozalsii* Levier; *Riccia cavernosa* Hoffm.; *Riccia sorocarpa* var. *heegii* et *Anthoceros agrestis* Paton).

REFERENCES

1. **Ahayoun K., Ouazzani Touhami A. & Douira A. 2007** — Inventaire des Bryophytes de l'Herbier "RAB" de l'Institut Scientifique (Rabat, Maroc), Documents de l'Institut Scientifique, Rabat, 21 : 71-89.
2. **Ahayoun K., Ouazzani Touhami A. & Douira A. 2008** — Étude des fructifications de *Lunularia cruciata*, bryophyte récoltée au Moyen-Atlas (Maroc) Bull. Mycol. Bot. Dauphiné-Savoie, 189 : 5-12.
3. **Ahayoun K., Ouazzani Touhami A. & Douira A. 2009** — *Riccia cavernosa* Hoffm. Emend. Raddi, hépatique rare, récoltée pour la première fois dans la plaine atlantique (Maroc). Cryptogamie, Bryologie, 30 (3): 389-394.
4. **Ahayoun K., Ouazzani Touhami A. Benkirane R. & Douira A. 2013** — Catalogue bibliographique des Bryophytes du Maroc (1913-2011). Journal of Animal & Plant Sciences, 17(1): 2433-2513.
5. **Amann J., 1924** — Contribution à la Bryologie du Maroc. Revue Bryologique, 51: 57-58.
6. **Augier J., 1966** — Flore des Bryophytes. Paris, Paul Lechevalier, 702 p.
7. **Bailly G., Vadam J.C. & Vergon J. P. 2004** — Guide pratique d'identification des Bryophytes aquatiques. Ministère de l'Écologie et du Développement Durable, 158 p.
8. **Boudier P., Chavoutier J., 2006** — Morphologie des Bryophytes. Bull. Mycol. Bot. Dauphiné- Savoie, 182: 23-45.
9. **Boulay M. 1904** — Muscinées de la France." Deuxième partie" Mousses. Ed. Paris. p : ILXXXII-LXXXVII, 224 p.
10. **B. L, Chaudhary1 and Vandana Vijaiavargiya, 2014.** Effect of light period on spore germination of *notothylas khasiana* udar et singh in half knop's liquid medium. Biolife. 2(3):708-711.
11. **Braun- blanquet J. & Maire R., 1924** — Etudes sur la végétation et la flore Marocaines. Mémoires de la Société des Sciences Naturelles du Maroc. N°VIII, première partie, p. 160-163.
12. **Casas C., Bruges M.; Cros R.M.; Sergio C.; Infante M., 2009** — Handbook of Liverworts and Hornworts of the Iberian Peninsula and the Balearic Islands: Illustrated Keys to Genera and Species. Institut d'Estudis Catalans. Barcelona, Spain, 177 p.
13. **Corbiere L., 1913a** — Contribution à la flore bryologique du Maroc, d'après les récoltes du Lieutenant Mouret. Revue Bryologique, 40: 7-13.
14. **Corbiere L., 1913b** — Nouvelle contribution à la flore bryologique du Maroc d'après les récoltes du Lieutnat Mouret. Revue Bryologique, 40: 51-57.
15. **Douin I. 1986** — Nouvelle Flore des Mousses et des Hépatiques. Paris, Berlin, p. 42-47.
16. **Fraval A. & Villemant C. 1997** — La Mâamora et ses ennemis. INRA, les dossiers de l'environnement, 15: 133-46.
17. **Gattefosse J. & Werner R.G. 1932** — Catalogus Bryophytum Marocanorum Adhuc Cognitorum. Bulletin de la Société des Sciences Naturelles et Physiques du Maroc, 12: 228-280.
18. **Gattefosse J. 1932** — Flore cryptogamique de la source thermale de Lalla Aïa. Bulletin de la Société des Sciences Naturelles du Maroc, 12: 164-167.
19. **Hill M. O., Bell N., Bruggeman-nannenga M.A., Bruges M., Cano M.J., Enroth J., Flatberg k.I., Frahm J.P., Gallego M.T., Garilleti R., Guerra J., Hedenas L., Holyoak D.T., Hyvonen J. & Ignatov M.S. 2006** — Bryological Monograph: An annotated checklist of the mosses of Europe and Macaronesia. Journal of Bryology, 28: 198–267.
20. **Jahns H. M. 1989** — Guide des fougères, mousses et lichens d'Europe. Lausanne, Delachaux et Niestlé, 258 p.
21. **Jean faubert (15/11/2007).** Flore des bryophytes du Québec- Labrador- la famille des Ricciaceae Dumort.- <http://www.floraquebeca.qc.ca/bryoweb>.
22. **Jelenc F. 1955a** — Muscinées de l'Afrique du Nord (Algérie, Tunisie, Maroc, Sahara). Société de Géographie et d'Archéologie de la province d'Oran 72, 73, 74, 75, 76 : 1-152.
23. **Jelenc F. 1966** — Contribution à l'étude de la flore et de la végétation bryologiques Nord-africaines (7^{ème} fascicule). Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique, 34 : 711-714.
24. **Jelenc F. 1967** — Muscinées de l'Afrique du Nord (Supplément). Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique, 35 (1-4): 186-215.
25. **Jovet-Ast S. 1955c** — *Riccia atromarginata* Lev. et sa variété *glabra* Lev. au Maroc. Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique, 24 (3-4): 240-247. Jovet-Ast S. 1955d — Hépatiques Marocaines I. Bulletin de la Société des Sciences Naturelles et Physiques du Maroc, 35(4): 265-282.
26. **Jovet-Ast S. 1956c** — Hépatiques Marocaines II Bulletin de la Société des Sciences Naturelles et Physiques du Maroc, XXXVI, premier trimestre, p. 43-60.

27. **Jovet-Ast S. 1961** — *Targionia lorbeeriana* K. M. Trois localités nouvelles. *Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique*, 30 (3-4): 278.
28. **Jovet-Ast S., 1966** — *Riccia crystallina* L. emend. Raddi et *Riccia cavernosa* Hoffm. emend. Raddi- II. *Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique*, 34, (1-2): 82-90.
29. **Jovet-Ast S. 1986** — Les *Riccia* de la région méditerranéenne. *Cryptogamie Bryologie Lichénologie* 7: 287-431.
30. **Jovet-Ast S. & Bischler H., 1966** — Les Hépatiques d'Israël: Enumération, notes écologiques et biogéographiques. *Revue Bryologique et Lichénologique* 25 (1-2): 91-126.
31. **Lacouture C. 1905** — Hépatiques de la France. Tableaux synoptiques des caractères saillants des tribus, des genres et des espèces. Paris, Paul Klincksieck, 78p.
32. **Maire R. & Werner R. G. 1934** — Contribution à la flore cryptogamique du Maroc. *Bulletin de la Société d'Histoire Naturelles d'Afrique du Nord*, 25(2) :40-60.
33. **Pierrot R.B., 1982**— Les bryophytes du Centre Ouest: classification, détermination, répartition. *Bulletin de la société botanique du Centre-Ouest*, nouvelle série, N°spécial 5, 123 p.
34. **Ros R.M., Mazimpaka V., Abou-Salama U., Aleffi M., Blockeel T.L., Brugués M., Cano M.J., Cros R.M., Dia M.G., Dirkse G.M., El Saadawi W., Erdag A., Ganeva A., González-mancebo J.M., Herrnstadt I., Khalil K., Kürschner H., Lanfranco E., Losada-lima A., Refai M.S., Rodríguez-núñez S., Abovljevic M., Sérgio C., Shabbara H., Sim-sim M. & Söderström L. 2007**— Hepatics and Anthocerotales of the Mediterranean, an annotated checklist. *Cryptogamie, Bryologie*, 28 (4): 351-437.
35. **Smith A.J.E., 1990** — *The liverworts of Britain and Ireland*. Cambridge, Cambridge University press, 362 p.
36. **Trabut L. 1941** — Flore des Hépatiques de l'Afrique du Nord. *Mélanges bryologiques et lichénologiques*, 12: 1-43.
37. **Watson E., 1981**—*British Mosses and Liverworts*. Cambridge, 3rd ed., 519 p

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